

Synthesis of Some New Mannich Bases Derived from Substituted Benzimidazole, Benzoxazol-2-one, Benzoxazol-2-thione, Oxadiazol-2-thiones and Their Biological Activities

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A number of 3-[4-substituted anilino] methyl benzoxazolin-2-one, benzoxazolin-2-thione, benzimidazole and 1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thione have been synthesised by Mannich reaction and were tested for their biological activities.

In recent years, benzazoles have been reported to possess antimicrobial^{1,2} activity. Antibacterial³, fungicidal⁴, anticonvulsant⁵ and insecticidal^{6,7} activities have also been reported in Mannich bases, derived from benzazoles. Substituted amino diphenyl ethers have been found to possess insecticidal⁸ activity. In continuation of our previous work⁹, we have now synthesised a series of new compounds by Mannich reaction using substituted benzazoles and substituted amino diphenyl ethers in alcohol. All the newly synthesised compounds have been screened for their insecticidal, bactericidal and fungicidal activities.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. All the synthesised compounds were characterised by i.r. spectroscopy, TLC and elemental analysis.

The intermediate benzazoles were prepared by known procedure¹⁰⁻¹² and were subjected to Mannich reaction with various new amines prepared by reported method⁹.

General method of synthesis of Mannich bases :

To a mixture of 0.01 mole of aryl amine in 35 ml ethanol and 0.01 mole of formaldehyde, 0.01 mole of heterocyclic base in ethanol was added slowly with stirring and kept overnight. The solid that separated, was filtered and crystallised from alcohol (Table 1). The Mannich bases were obtained in 80-90% yield.

Biological activities :

The newly synthesised compounds were evaluated for their insecticidal activity against cockroaches, following the method of Nash¹³. Antibacterial

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activity of these compounds against *Bacillus subtilis* and *Bacillus pumilus* were determined following the agar plate diffusion method¹⁴. Few compounds were also screened for their fungicidal activity against *Fusarium roseum* following the method of Horshfall¹⁵.

For insecticidal activity, the solution of test compounds were prepared in two concentrations viz., 0.5% and 0.1% in acetone. The 0.02 ml of the solution was injected between 4th and 5th segment of the insect from posterior side. All the experiments were carried out in duplicate and the results, as given in Table 1, indicate a mean value. For antibacterial activity, 10 mg/ml of acetone solution was prepared for each compound and filter paper discs saturated with the test solution were placed on the nutrient agar. The results of the antibacterial activity also given in Table 1, indicate a mean value.

TABLE 1—BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITIES OF THE MANNICH BASES

Sl. No	R ₁	R	M.P. °C	Fungicidal activity against <i>Fusarium roseum</i>		Antibacterial activity against <i>B. subtilis</i> and <i>B. pumilus</i>		Insecticidal activity against cockroaches. Mean K.D. time (hrs.)	
				Concentration	% Inhibition	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>B. pumilus</i>	% concentration 0.5	% concentration 0.1
1.	Phenoxy	3-benzoxazolin-2-onyl	138	1 : 1,000 1 : 10,000 1 : 100,000	12.5 0.0 0.0	—	—	8.0	9.5
2.	p-Cl phenoxy	„	170	1 : 1,000 1 : 10,000 1 : 1,00,000	37.5 25.0 12.5	—	—	12.0	14.0
3.	Morpholino	„	168	1 : 1,000 1 : 10,000 1 : 1,00,000	37.5 32.5 22.5	+++	—	18.5	20.0
4.	Phenoxy	6-Cl-3-benzoxazolin-2-onyl	175-76	1 : 1,000 1 : 10,000 1 : 1,00,000	15.0 0.0 0.0	—	++	25.0	30.0
5.	p-Cl phenoxy	„	164-65	1 : 1,000 1 : 10,000 1 : 1,00,000	32.5 22.5 2.5	+++	++	12.0	14.0
6.	Morpholino	„	172	1 : 1,000 1 : 10,000 1 : 1,00,000	42.5 27.5 17.5	—	—	17.0	19.5
7.	Phenoxy	6-NO ₂ -3-benzoxazolin-2-onyl	147-48	—	—	—	—	21.0	25.0
8.	p-Cl phenoxy	„	160	—	—	+++	+++	17.5	19.0
9.	Morpholino	„	173	1 : 1,000 1 : 10,000 1 : 1,00,000	10.0 0.0 0.0	—	—	13.0	15.5
10.	Phenoxy	3-benzoxazolin-2-thionyl	132	—	—	—	++	15.0	19.0
11.	p-Cl phenoxy	„	169	—	—	—	++	17.0	19.5
12.	Morpholino	„	166	1 : 1,000 1 : 10,000 1 : 1,00,000	30.0 15.0 5.0	—	++	21.0	25.0
13.	Phenoxy	1-benzimidazolyl	152	—	—	+++	+++	24.0	27.0
14.	p-Cl phenoxy	„	148	—	—	+++	+++	18.0	21.0
15.	Morpholino	„	176	1 : 1,000 1 : 10,000 1 : 1,00,000	45.0 32.5 22.5	+++	++	21.0	25.0
16.	Morpholino	2-Me-1-benzimidazolyl	188	1 : 1,000 1 : 10,000 1 : 1,00,000	32.5 27.5 15.0	++	++	18.5	19.0
17.	Phenoxy	3-[5-(4-Cl-phenoxy)methyl]-1,3,4-oxadiazolin-2-thionyl	138	—	—	—	—	15.0	17.0
18.	p-Cl phenoxy	„	139	—	—	—	—	17.0	19.5
19.	Phenoxy	3-[5-(2,4-dichlorophenoxy)methyl]-1,3,4-oxadiazolin-2-thionyl	136	—	—	—	—	19.5	23.5
20.	p-Cl-phenoxy	„	80	—	—	++	++	23.0	25.0
21.	Phenoxy	3-[5-(4-Me-phenoxy)methyl]-1,3,4-oxadiazolin-2-thionyl	145	—	—	—	++	17.5	18.5
22.	p-Cl phenoxy	„	133	—	—	+++	++	13.5	15.5
23.	Phenoxy	3-[5-(2-Me-phenoxy)methyl]-1,3,4-oxadiazolin-2-thionyl	132	—	—	—	++	15.0	19.0
24.	p-Cl phenoxy	„	131	—	—	—	—	19.0	21.0

— = No inhibition ; + = Zone size 6-8 mm. ; ++ = Zone size 8-10 mm. ; +++ = Zone size 11-15 mm. ; ++++ = Zone size greater than 15 mm.

From the results obtained, it is proved that all the compounds possess significant biological activities. Compounds no. 1, 2, 5, 9, 22 (Table 1) exhibit better insecticidal activity than the other compounds. Compound no. 1 has been found to be most potent for its insecticidal activity. Further, it has been observed that the Mannich bases prepared from substituted benzazolin-2-one and oxadiazolin-2-thionyl possess more pronounced insecticidal activity than the compounds derived from benzimidazoles.

Compounds no. 3, 5, 8, 13, 14, 15, 16, 20 and 22 showed inhibition against *B. subtilis* while inhibition against *B. pumilus* was observed in compounds no. 4, 5, 8, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 20, 21, 22 and 23. Further, it has also been proved that the compounds obtained from benzimidazole, possess better antibacterial activity than the compounds obtained from other derivatives.

Few of the compounds were also screened for their fungicidal activity. From the results obtained,

it has been found that morpholino derivatives possess better fungicidal activities. Compounds no. 2, 3, 5, 6, 15 and 16 possess moderate activity. Mannich bases synthesised from benzimidazole showed better inhibition than the compounds obtained from benzoxazole substituted compounds.

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